

ANGLIA RUSKIN UNIVERSITY

Dissertation Declaration

Title of Award

BA HONS Criminology

Date

24/04/23

SID Number

1907621

Name of Supervisor

Victoria Gadd

Title of Dissertation

Labelling theory and moral panics and the links to youth deviancy

Word Count

10,000

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Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the following people without whom I would not have made it through this degree. Mother (Salvina) and sister (Francesca) who reminded me to work hard and not give up. My supervisor and lecturer Vicky for always giving me advice and aiding my academic development over the last 3 years and finally my friends for reminding me to keep my head up and concentrate.

Abstract-

This dissertation will be identifying the key concepts of labelling theory and moral panics in order to locate the various links to youth deviancy and how it can be affected. The topic is considerably important due to the levels at which moral panics can impact communities and increase labelling among minority youths. The gaps in the research are clear, there is not enough research regarding the links to youth deviancy and how moral panics can be exacerbated to the point where there is an increased level of youth deviancy. There is also little research on the perceptions of youth in day-to-day policing and how moral panics and subsequent labelling may have an effect on it. The research is solely literature based which will help identify key points from previous literature on the topic and identify whether or not it is currently relevant in modern society. The dissertation found that there is an increased level of bias within the police which may be a manifestation of moral panics and labelling whilst the dissertation also discovered that the media is key to fuelling a moral panic within society especially in the context of youth deviance.

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Introduction-

Because of their major links to youth deviancy, the theoretical concepts of labelling theory and moral panic have been extensively investigated in criminological literature. The act of assigning an identity to an individual or a certain group is referred to as labelling (Bernburg, 2019). The notion of labelling investigates how it can have a wide range of effects for those who have been tagged as deviant or criminal, as well as those who are believed to be offending (Bernburg, 2019). The concept of "labelling" has been utilised by theorists to investigate how it might directly affect and induce moral panics. Findings within this area would be extremely important to identify as these occurrences can have an incredible impact on society and significant effects on communities that are heavily labelled. A moral panic is an occurrence created by a group or individuals engaged in immoral or deviant behaviour according to societal standards. It is frequently characterised by heightened worry and panic, which spreads swiftly throughout society resulting in an exaggerated and disproportionate response of disagreement (Cohen, 1972). Labelling, from a theoretical standpoint, can cause moral panics because individuals or groups stigmatised within society and continuously classified as deviant may become increasingly deviant and hostile. A moral panic may emerge during this process as those who are classified refuse to embrace social norms and morality (Cohen, 1972). In practice, this elicits a strong reaction from society, which focuses only on the activities of the group or individual, rather than how they became stigmatised within society (Critcher, 2013).

Furthermore, the impact of labelling theory and moral panics on young people is becoming a growing concern among academics and authorities. It is commonly acknowledged that young people are more prone to labelling and stigma (Fatsis, 2019). Young individuals who are classified as deviant or criminal may face serious consequences, including school

expulsion, difficulties gaining employment and being targeted by police authorities (Fatsis, 2019). This can create a vicious cycle of deviance that is difficult to break. As a result, increased media scrutinization continues which in turn increases the awareness around the topic. Inevitably, an increased awareness invites the fear and anxiety caused by moral panics to result in a "rush to judge", in which young people are classified as deviant or criminal without sufficient evidence. This can have serious consequences for young people and deepen existing social inequality. Historically, there have been several moral panics in recent history, such as the war on drugs and the anti-vaccine movement/panic (Critcher, 2013). Drill music is a contemporary moral panic that will be analysed within this dissertation it has influenced our reaction to teenage deviance. Drill music's moral panic is a complicated issue that incorporates a number of social and cultural elements, including race and age inequalities. Unfortunately, these are factors that cannot be controlled therefore, this inevitably leaves young members of the community at risk to further labelling which has seen to increase stigmatisation. Artists and producers frequently consider the genre as a reflection and depiction of the harsh and complex realities of living in underprivileged neighbourhoods (Ilan, 2019).

The majority of Drill music addresses violent issues that arise in these communities, such as knife crime, murder, and drug culture (Ilan, 2019). The moral panic of Drill music will be analysed as a case study to identify the effects of excessive labelling and how moral panics can alter police perception of young people. In recent years, these issues have become incredibly prevalent in recent years due to the effects of labelling and moral panics. This dissertation will solely use secondary research to identify significant information in order to derive further understanding of the topic. A literature review will be conducted where key

concepts and authors will be analysed in order to locate the research gaps that the dissertation will look to fill. This will identify significant concepts that are incredibly important to the majority of the research that is discussed within this dissertation. These concepts are extremely important this is due to the fact that they explain and identify situations in which the effects of labelling and moral panics can have the most impact. These concepts include, the iatrogenic effects of juvenile justice, circular logic within labelling and the self-fulfilling prophecy. These concepts will be acknowledged and researched in the context of contemporary moral panics and also the police perceptions of youth deviance.

The aim of this research will aim to contribute to understanding the connections between the likelihood of youth deviancy when the effects of moral panics and labelling are present. Due to this dissertation, identifying different factors such as police perceptions and using Drill music as a case study will enable this research to increase the understanding and awareness of these different factors and how they may also present themselves. This project will also aim to identify similarities and differences between the original literature of moral panics and contemporary moral panics in order to identify changes that may have occurred over time such as the influence of the media and the creation and impact of social media on moral panics and labelling. Social media within recent years has developed considerably and has had a significant effect on the way that crime news is presented, this has the potential to create extrmeme change in the way moral panics occur. This dissertation also aims to create recommendations in order to combat the effects of moral panics and labelling towards young people in order to combat an increased level of youth deviance. These recommendations will be derived from thorough research on the topic and

will be centred around the police force and the current training that they receive whilst there will also be recommendations on how to combat the labelling of communities through the platforms of terrestrial media and social media. The literature on labelling theory and moral panics is extensive, and it has influenced criminological literature. However, the literature on the relationship between these notions and teenage deviancy is still lacking (Fatsis, 2019). The fundamental purpose of this research is to discover the connections between labelling theories, moral panics, and teenage deviance. The literature review will look at studies on each of these topics, as well as gaps in the literature, to identify areas and concepts that could benefit from more research. This dissertation aims to contribute to the continuing conversation regarding teenage deviancy; How it is viewed, and how society might better understand it in order to avoid it by investigating the relationships between labelling theories and moral panics. This is an essential part of the research as it will provide further backing for the recommendations given at the end of the dissertation. This will be done by analysing significant literature in order to understand how different factors within can influence judgement and have an impact on youth deviancy.

Chapter 1- Literature review

Labelling theory has been used by academics to explore links between youth deviancy and crime. This has been done over a number of years, many studies have been conducted in order to identify scenarios in which young individuals may be affected by constant labelling. The theory of labelling theory was introduced in the book "Outsiders" by Howard Becker, since then labelling theory has shaped criminological literature has become a constant topic amongst academics. The term "Labelling" refers to the act of placing an identity upon an individual or a specific group (Ugwudike, 2015), (Farrington, 2014). Theorists have used the concept of "labelling" to explore how it can lead to many consequences for those individuals who have been labelled as deviant or criminal. As well as those individuals who are perceived to be offending (Farrington, 2014) Within this dissertation, moral panics will also be considered to have links to youth deviancy. Moral panics are events caused by a group or individuals engaging in acts that are considered immoral or deviant by societal standards (Critcher, 2011). Labelling theory has strong connections to moral panics theoretically and practically. Within a theoretical perspective, labelling can directly affect and cause moral panics. For instance, a group that is stigmatised within society and labelled consistently as deviant may become increasingly deviant and aggressive (Critcher, 2011). This is due to the fact that the group or individual will inhibit the label as their own self-identity. During this process a moral panic may ensue as those who are labelled will refuse to accept societies laws and morals. In practice this creates a strong reaction from society which will solely focus on the actions of the group or individual, rather than how they became stigmatised within society and what went wrong within society to allow those actions to occur in the first place (Dandoy, 2014). The literature around the two ideas is enormous, and this review will break it down in order to find gaps in the literature while also evaluating the correlations that may suggest to growing links to youth deviancy. The goals of this literature review are to identify the links between labelling theories and moral panics and youth deviancy. The literature review will look into studies on both of these themes. Following that, gaps in

the literature will be reviewed to identify subjects and concepts that may benefit from additional research.

Within labelling theory there are many prominent authors, for example Howard Becker and Edwin Lemert. Lemert identified a typology amongst deviance consisting of primary and secondary deviance. In doing so Lemert identified the stages of which deviancy affects an individual which is a considerable addition to the theory itself (Williams, Mcshane and Lemert, 2016). This contribution to labelling theory provides a timeline to the rate at which an individual is labelled, this is done by identifying primary deviance as an action where the individual does not regard themselves as deviant whilst engaging in an act that is considered deviant. Secondary deviance, however, is the individual reacting to the way society has viewed their actions this occurs generally through name calling and stereotyping. This study is incredibly important as it gives reasoning as to why deviancy may be amplified once the original deviant act had occurred. Lemert goes further on to explain that although many young people may commit deviant acts however only a select amount will be stigmatised and deemed a delinquent individual. This is extremely relevant in the modern day as it provides a time frame and also explains why deviancy may be amplified due to further stigmatisation another cause of amplification would be moral panics.

Howard Becker, another prominent author who in which has contributed significantly within the realm of labelling theory. Becker's addition to the theory stemmed from the idea that, deviance is a direct result or consequence of external judgement. Becker identified that within society there are individuals and groups who in which are not inherently evil/deviant until they subsequently identified with that image in mind. This formulation of labelling theory was created from social interactionist theories. These authors have contributed an enormous amount of information and research in order to identify ways in which labelling theory can address different scenarios where individuals are labelled.

In order to identify all links to youth deviancy research has also been conducted on the theory of moral panics, this theory has significant links to labelling theory and also youth deviancy. It has also remained extremely relevant and is still used as an important concept in the modern day. Stanley Cohen is one of the most significant and prominent authors regarding moral panics. The author of *Folk Devils and Moral Panics* had identified different stages of moral panics and how different agencies such as the media portray certain ideologies that can help segregate different communities from society (Mannion and Small, 2019). His most widely known work focused on the mods and rockers groups and the altercations between the two that occurred in 1964 (Mannion and Small, 2019). Through this work the social theory of moral panics was created. Cohen describes moral panics as a process used by a form of government as a call to action to in order to address a new threat to the fabric of society (Mannion and Small, 2019). The response to the moral panic will result in a substantial emphasis of control amongst the deviant group. Cohens work was significant to the studies of moral panics (Critcher, 2013).

This is due to Cohen identifying the role of the mass media and how they can contribute to the way that these moral panics should be handled and solved (Critcher, 2013). Alongside Stanley Cohen, Jock Young is another prominent author within the topic of moral panics. Jock Youngs work consists of developing many key concepts within the theory of moral panics. These concepts such as late modernity and amplification. The concept of Late modernity was developed alongside young's work within moral panics as his research surrounding moral panics was placed within a wider theoretical framework of late modernity (Young, 2007). Which identified the changing nature of cultural and social institutions in a contemporary society (Young, 2007). This is an extremely important concept for the study of moral panics. This is due to it aiding an explanation as to why moral panics emerge in comparison to previous eras of modernity which were defined by stability and order (Young, 2007). Young identifies issues with late modernity such as rapid change and uncertainty plaguing today's society (Young, 2007).

1.1- Key concepts of Labelling theory and Moral panics theory

There are several essential notions under labelling theory; these concepts evolve through time and can also be modified by real-time occurrences. For example, the process of social exclusion occurs over time. While the effects of labelling begin to take place, the individual begins to adopt the label that has been assigned to them as their new self-identity.

A key concept within labelling theory is the iatrogenic effect of juvenile justice (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). This concept suggests, that due to the increased interaction with authorities and judicial systems through an individual's adolescent years can prompt increased deviant actions and behaviour (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). This concept has also identified that small interactions with the justice system may have a positive effect on the individual and may assist them in desisting from criminal activities (Hill and Maughan, 2001). However, as outlined in the research, the more constrictive and negative the interactions with the justice system can be considerably damaging to a young person's development. This is due to the impact that the label will have on the young individual and how quickly they may adopt the new label as their self-identity as previously mentioned once the new label is adopted it is increasingly likely that further deviant behaviour will occur (Hill and Maughan, 2001). This is an important concept to consider as although the justice system is functioning as it is required when a crime is committed it may do more harm than good to the individual who has committed the crime. This has severe implications for labelling as individuals coming into contact with the justice system at a young age can prompt them to be labelled by peers and family members, then labelling is causing individuals to commit acts of deviancy whilst also being labelled further after coming into contact with the justice system (McAra and McVie, 2012).

A significant consequence of labelling a young person as deviant is the associated process of social exclusion. This concept identifies the issues with labelling, the most prominent is the impact and exclusion from friendships and close relationships (Krohn *et al.*, 2019). This is due to the

stigmatisation that surrounds many labels. Secondary labelling is the next process during this period there is a number of situations that can occur apart from impacts among close relationships, it is also a likelihood that many opportunities will be excluded also (Krohn *et al.*, 2019). This concept identifies that due to the stigmatisation those regarded as peers and community members devalue and disregard the individual. Link identifies that the features of the stigmatised label (criminal offender) result in people becoming afraid of the individual which leads to complete social exclusion from the community and in some cases society itself (Link, 1982). Due to the stigmatisation that follows individuals labelled as deviant their friendship groups may be restricted this may lead them to associate with deviant groups (Link, 1982). This according to Link is for the purpose of receiving a positive image of themselves from a significant peer. Ultimately, this concept is extremely important to identify as during adolescence the social bonds that are developed with family and peers are extremely crucial to development (Link, 1982). However, as identified in the research involvement in groups considered deviant can reduce social bonds and significant life changes.

However, labelling theory has had much criticism since its inception. One of the criticisms of labelling is the fact that in some cases it appears to use circular logic. This is due to the fact that it identifies deviance as a behaviour that is labelled and subsequently rationalises the outburst of deviance by explaining that it occurs due to being labelled (DAVIS, 1973). Therefore, the argument is circular in logic, this is an important criticism as the theory can act in this way occasionally if there are no other external factors that may prompt deviant behaviour other than labelling. This is also the case if the theory is taken in parts and not as a whole (DAVIS, 1973), (KLEIN, 1986). (KLEIN, 1986), also identified a strong level of ambiguity and complexity amongst labelling processes, which can further identify reasoning surrounding the criticism of the theory.

There are various key concepts that identify links to youth deviancy through the means of moral panics. However, the concepts that this literature review will be identifying include, the deviance amplification spiral and the concept of folk devils. The two concepts being discussed often have

significant ties to labelling theory, they also acknowledge the exclusion of groups and individuals from society due to effects of labelling causing a moral panic (Spicer, 2021). The deviance amplification spiral was first created by Leslie Wilkins and further developed by prominent authors Stanley Cohen and Jock Young (Spicer, 2021). Throughout their research in the 1960's concerning the British moral panic known as the Mods and Rockers (Spicer, 2021). During this time, they identified the ways that societal anxieties can be amplified through contact with the media (Spicer, 2021). These findings prompted their discovery of the spiral itself, identifying a cycle in which deviancy amplification does not stop and only becomes worse through constant self-reinforcement. This occurs until change or reformation is created through new legislation, or in the context of sub-youth culture the deviant groups may group up and begin to desist from deviant behaviour and ideologies (Jewkes, 2015, pp. 88–89). There are many criticisms regarding the concepts mentioned in regard to the theory and recognition of moral panics. The criticisms of the deviancy amplification spiral have been critiqued as placing a heavy emphasis on labelling and the processes behind it (Johnson, Simons and Conger, 2004). Many critics have directed their criticism towards the fact that the amplification spiral may simplify complex sociological and political factors that may also have influence on deviance rather than labelling being the main factor at fault (Johnson, Simons and Conger, 2004). These criticisms are of interest within the literature examined and coupled with a contemporary moral panic in later chapters will be of considerable help in identifying further links to youth deviancy.

Understanding this concept is significant to unravelling the cultural and social factors that contribute to the stigmatisation and exclusion of groups and individuals from society which can propel and increase youth deviance (Spicer, 2021). The term "Folk devils" was derived by Stanley Cohen, during his work on the Mods and Rockers moral panic which as previously mentioned occurred within the 1960's (Marsh and Melville, 2011). A folk devil is defined as an ostracised individual or group who is

deemed a threat to society and the moral that the society holds (Jewkes, 2015, pp. 298). The concept of folk devils is applicable to many situations such as the demonisation of immigrants and ethnic minorities. However, the concept of folk devils is a dangerous concept, due to the demonisation of groups usually occurring through increased levels of labelling within society. This can lead to an increased level of deviance amongst those groups (Brisman and South, 2015). This allows further labelling of the individuals which in turn creates the Spiral of deviance amplification which has been mentioned previously. The correlation between these two concepts is very prevalent amongst literature concerning moral panics (Brisman and South, 2015).

1.2 - Gaps in the literature

In reference to labelling theory and moral panics there are various gaps in the literature, many of these gaps stem from the lack of research carried out and from the sole research on the negative effects of labelling. One of the areas that lacks research is the level of analysis focused on the individual. The gap has identified a need for further research that focuses on other factors that can contribute to deviant acts. There has also been insufficient research carried out regarding the long-term effects of labelling amongst individuals and communities. Through the research conducted within this project it is clear to see that research surrounding the short-term effects of labelling have been considered and the theory and research surrounding it may benefit from further research considering the long term affects to the individual's life course (Maruna, 2013). The gap regarding the long-term effects of labelling is an important area to analyse due to many researchers identifying that the age crime curve has not changed in at least 150 years (Gottfredson and Hirschi, 1990), whilst many labelling theorists have also identified that it is near impossible to strip an individual of the deviant label once it has been internalised (Maruna, 2013). There has been insufficient research on the deviancy amplification spiral in the context of the recent banning of Drill music and the

conviction of individuals for using lyrics that are seen to incite violence. This project aims to identify further research on this topic due to its prevalence within today's society. This research will be of significant importance as the genre "Drill" has become somewhat of a moral panic in recent times. Whilst this is the case, the moral panic of Drill music has also stemmed from the increased labelling of young people this is another topic in which will be researched thoroughly within this project.

In conclusion, researchers have studied labelling theory and moral panics in depth to identify how they relate to juvenile crime and deviance. Labelling is the process of imposing an identity on an individual or group (Ugwudike, 2015), which can have negative implications for individuals who are labelled as deviant or criminal (Farrington, 2014). The notion of moral panics, on the other hand, describes events that occur as a result of activities that are judged immoral or deviant by societies standards, resulting in heightened control and stigmatisation of the deviant group (Citcher, 2011). The literature around these two theories is extensive, and it has greatly contributed to our understanding of deviancy and its repercussions on individuals and society. Famous authors in labelling theory include Howard Becker and Edwin Lemert, as well as Stanley Cohen and Jock Young. The evaluation of the literature has discovered, gaps in the literature and examined connections that suggest developing ties to youth deviancy, highlighting the need for future research in this field. Overall, labelling theory and moral panics provide important insights into how societal norms and expectations affect the lives of individuals and communities (Citcher, 2011). In short, labelling theory describes how labels assigned by society can impact a person's behaviour. It addresses several essential themes, such as the iatrogenic effect of juvenile justice, which implies that encounters with the court system might lead to aberrant behaviour in young people (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). Stigmatisation leads to exclusion from friendships and other life possibility, which is a key consequence of labelling. Although, labelling theory has been criticised for its circular logic and ambiguity, it remains a significant idea in understanding deviance. The deviance amplification spiral and the concept of folk devils are both related to labelling theory and emphasise the exclusion of groups and individuals from society as a result of moral panics. Overall, labelling theory and its

accompanying concepts provide an insight on the complicated relationship that exists between social identity and behaviour. Labelling theory is a sociological viewpoint that emphasises how the social labels that people are assigned can have a substantial impact on their behaviour and how they are regarded by others (Link, 1982). While much study has been conducted on the detrimental consequences of labelling, there are still several gaps in the literature that must be filled.

The level of analysis centred on the individual is one of the gaps found in the literature, as is the necessity for additional study to address other key elements that may lead to deviant behaviour. Furthermore, limited studies have been conducted on the long-term impacts of labelling on individuals and communities, which is an important field for investigation given that labelling theorists believe it could be difficult to erase a deviant label after it has been internalised. The absence of studies on the long-term impacts of labelling is especially concerning given that the age crime curve hasn't changed in at least 150 years (Gottfredson and Hirschi, 1990). Furthermore, there has been a lack of studies conducted on the deviancy amplification spiral in the context of the recent ban on Drill music and the conviction of individuals for utilising lyrics that are perceived to promote violence. Evidently this, is an important problem in today's society, as the Drill genre has sparked a moral panic. This project's research intends to fill these gaps in the literature and provide insight into the long-term effects of labelling on people and communities. Furthermore, given the prominence of moral panics surrounding these issues, this study aims to identify additional research on the topic of the deviancy amplification spiral in the context of Drill music and the rising labelling of young people.

Chapter 2: Moral Panic in contemporary society – The case of Drill music

There have been a considerable number of moral panics in recent history, such as the war on drugs and the anti-vaccine movement/panic. However, one of the contemporary moral panics that has affected our response to youth deviancy is Drill music. The moral panic surrounding Drill music is a complex matter and is multifaceted, the moral panic concerning Drill music involves a variety of social and cultural factors, including race and generational differences. The genre is often regarded as a reflection and depiction of the harsh and complex realities of living within disadvantaged communities by artists and producers (Ilan, 2019). Drill music does discuss violent matters that occur in these areas. For example, artists may mention violent acts, such as knife crime, murder and drug culture which is also a topic that is often mentioned within the genre. This is due to harsh realities being presented in a raw format which many people may find uneasy to identify with. Whilst some of the artists may be involved in street violence, many of the artists use Drill music as a career possibility to escape these areas (Moore and Stuart, 2021). However, throughout the duration of 2016 and onwards after the Metropolitan police identified the genre as a key factor in youth violence, the stigmatisation around the Drill music community increased, which made the possibility of a career within the genre considerably more difficult. (Ilan, 2019). Due to the increased stigmatisation within society towards the genre, it is also made difficult by the increased police attention focused on the artists. Drill music originated in Chicago (USA) in the early 2010's. In the years 2010-present Drill music has been identified and labelled as a genre that has the ability to incite violence amongst the younger generations (Ireland *et al.*, 2020). Due to this, the government had authorised the Metropolitan police and other law enforcement services to employ controversial tactics such as limiting the amount of music that Drill artists can release and where they are allowed to perform; in order to limit the damage that the genre could possibly cause (Fatsis, 2019).

Drill music and its predecessor genre “Grime” has been accused of promoting drug use and causing the sharp rise in violent crime by black Britons in deprived areas of London by the Metropolitan police and also by many media outlets (Fatsis, 2019). Due to the media depiction and demonisation of Drill music and the surrounding culture it has become increasingly difficult to associate the genre with anything else other than violence and death (Fatsis, 2019). Many media outlets have referred to and acknowledged Drill music as a leading contributing factor to violent crime and gang involvement (Pinkney and Robinson-Edwards, 2018) leading to a moral panic regarding Drill music and its effects. Labelling theory has played a significant part in this moral panic, due to the labelling of the fans, the artists, and the genre itself as deviant and criminal in nature (Monteith, 2022). There is currently a growing consensus amongst academics and journalists that Drill music has become a victim of labelling (Monteith, 2022). This refers to the aforementioned process in which a negative label or stereotype is applied to something based on limited evidence. Subsequently, this has had significant impacts on the genre such as a limitation on new artists making music.

2.1- Background of the Drill music Moral panic

In 2018, the UK Government implemented a ban on Drill music, this ban aimed to stop performance and distribution of Drill music and subsequent violent music videos (Scott, 2020). Critics of the ban have identified that it unfairly targets a particular cultural form and also minority groups, they also identified that the ban could have a significant effect on freedom of expression amongst young individuals in society (Chapman, 2021). This may occur, due to an increased interaction with the police as this would be a significant implication as it may limit what music artists are capable of doing within their work.

A report conducted by the Centre for Crime and Justice Studies, argued that the ban was put in place in order to divert attention away from useful policies and effective approaches to reduce youth violence and deviance. (Chapman, 2021). This includes effective approaches such as youth centres

and also increased education within the community (Forss Norstedt and Malmqvist, 2021). The Motivation for the ban on Drill music was to supposedly combat the risk and harm caused by the genre and the greater risk of increased cases of youth crime. The ban also allowed the authorities to hand out Criminal Behaviour Orders (CBO) to Drill artists (Scott, 2020). These prevented artists from engaging with certain individuals and entering certain areas whilst also limiting what artists were allowed to wear including the restriction of wearing hoods. Five members of a Drill group known as 1011 were given a CBO this required them to give 24hrs notice to any music being released and 48hrs warning of a live performance with the location date and time given to the authorities (Chapman, 2021). This was a heavily criticised action with academics and musicians criticising the ban at the time, this was due to the increased policing within the genre and the threat to the freedom of expression, which is a significant part of the culture and community of Grime and Drill. The criticism of this action was extremely public, whilst academics also identified that many authors and musicians that are now celebrated would not have been able to thrive under such limitations (Chapman, 2021). For example, Rap artist Eminem (Marshall Mathers) was heavily critiqued and viewed as a bad influence in the public view for a number of years due to his violent and misogynistic lyrics (Jewkes, 2015). However, he did not come into contact with the significant amount of critique as did Drill music. Furthermore, if Eminem and his lyrics was criticised as heavily as Drill music it would've been significantly likely that he would not have been able to survive under such pressures during the beginning of his career. This would've likely led to the music he created not having as much an impact as it originally did and subsequently his career may have been affected as the ban would have significantly hindered Drill artists.

Many academics have pointed out that the ban reflects multiple concerns over the way marginalised groups are represented in the media and society as a whole (Ilan, 2019). The concerns, such as the limitation of freedom of expression and the marginalisation and increased scrutinisation of young black men within society are extremely prevalent within this moral panic. The concerns reinforce the demonisation of young black males within society (Chapman, 2021). These concerns are also

identifying extreme implications for the media as the articles and headlines also portray an increasingly worrying depiction of young black men, which has hindered their ability to engage society in various ways including the ability to create music without hindrance.

This chapter has identified that the coverage of Drill music within the media only reinforced negative and harmful stereotypes regarding young black Britons (Johnson, Simons and Conger, 2004). This project has identified that once the media began sensationalising the topic of the ban and Drill music all together it was clear that a moral panic would form. It has been noted by several academics, that there are extreme concerns surrounding the moral panic concerning Drill music such as the lack of freedom of expression and the increased scrutinisation of young black men. The basis for this concern stems from the inability to create and express oneself. As well as impacts for artists that create Drill music such as police intervention in the creation of music (Due to the ban in 2018). There are significant implications for artists if they were to respond to these concerns, such as an increased risk of breaking conditions set out in the 2018 ban and an increased likelihood of receiving a CBO (Fatsis, 2019). These concerns have stemmed from the moral panic itself and the societal reaction that it has received. It has also been identified that the concerns surrounding Drill music could act as a springboard for further censorship and suppression of black and minority ethnic artists this is due to the increased police presence and perception of young black males (Pinkney and Robinson-Edwards, 2018). This is a concerning and direct effect that has been caused by a mixture of the moral panic and an increased level of labelling. A subsequent issue of increased censoring would be the decrease in artistic expression amongst the younger generations; in which is often viewed as a voice for marginalized communities to create and aid with social change (Fatsis, 2019).

2.2 -Theoretical effects

Labelling theory has played a significant part in the increased stigmatisation and creation of the moral panic surrounding Drill music. Labelling theory has existed in many cultures in recent history, this is seen with increased labelling of drug users as deviant within the USA and with the increased labelling of LGBTQ+ community as immoral and deviant. This has also led to moral panics within the USA which have caused significant issues with many communities. Whereas increased labelling of young black males has also been seen in the UK (Bernburg, 2019). Due to the increased stigmatisation that young black males have faced within their communities Drill music has been labelled as extremely violent and deviant by the Metropolitan Police and a number of media outlets which has led to the creation of the moral panic (Bernburg, 2019). Due to this significant increase in labelling and the heavily criticised ban that was set in place in 2018 criminalising aspects of artistic expression. There is a strong possibility that Drill artists may have come into increased contact with the juvenile justice system (Scott, 2020). Many Drill artists are young males (Ilan, 2019), and coming into contact with the justice system, at a young age can be significantly detrimental to their future development (Scott, 2020). There are extreme implications to this as contact with the justice system at a young age may impact opportunities such as future job prospects as increased labelling surrounding those in contact with the justice system is a prevalent matter and one that holds a significant weight in society. As previously mentioned within Chapter 1, this effect is known as the iatrogenic effect of juvenile justice (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). The increase in labelling due to many of the artists coming into contact with the justice system at a young age, which may have exacerbated the effects that created the moral panic surrounding the genre (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). Monteith (2022), identified that using Drill music lyrics and music videos to secure criminal convictions is one of if not the most deep-rooted examples of systemic racism within the UK. This identifies that, tactics used by prosecutors, are victimising young artist (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). Furthermore, the idea of using one's lyrics as evidence is not seen in a range of other

scenarios and cases, this identifies that Drill music has been labelled consistently which has subsequently increased the level of victimisation that Drill artists have faced (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). This in turn helps position Drill music artists as, what Cohen (1972) described as folk devils.

Once Drill artists had been positioned as folk devils, it inherently caused a number of issues, these issues include psychological issues in which may present as shame, guilt, and anxiety (Waite-Jones and Rodriguez, 2022). Individuals labelled as folk devils, may also feel a loss of reputation which can have impacts on future work. This in turn has identified a link between labelling theory and an increased possibility of youth deviancy through the increased contact with the justice system and the labelling that subsequently follows. This is incredibly important to identify as this may cause significant issues in the future for a number of young people. This is important to address as there are also additional factors that has allowed this link to youth deviancy to become increasingly prevalent within today's society (Scott, 2020). These external factors include and are not limited to, government involvement (2018 Ban on Drill music) this heightened awareness to the increased scrutinisation that Drill music was receiving (Scott, 2020). The second notable factor was the increased scrutinisation through media outlets due to the supposed newsworthiness which kept the articles circulating (Jewkes, 2015). The role that the media played within this moral panic was extremely concerning, the increased level of stigmatisation which enabled further labelling to occur was fundamental to inciting the moral panic (Jewkes, 2015). Drill music holds a significant news value in violence and conflict, this fuels the medias desire to present events regarding violence and conflict in a dramatic and even graphic fashion. (Jewkes, 2015) also identifies that violence humiliation and cruelty are often objectified in the media and are frequently used as a commodity to be distributed through media outlets to be "pleasurably consumed". The news reports that were presented within the media were kept in circulation for several weeks at a time which in turn fuelled the moral panic concerning Drill artists (Jewkes, 2015).

Following on from the links that have been identified within moral panics and links to youth deviancy, it is clear to see that Cohen's original work on the studies of moral panics is still relevant in the context of contemporary moral panics (Ben-Yehuda, 2009). This is due to an increase in similarities within contemporary moral panics that were also found prior to this in Cohen's original study (Ben-Yehuda, 2009). The similarities that have been found are an increased level of stigmatisation between one or more community and an increased level of news reports regarding them (Herdt, 2009). Drill music's uprising within the UK had also coincided with a broader cultural movement, young black men were perceived in the media as a threat to societal order (Chapman, 2021). Therefore, using this it is extremely clear that Cohen's original work is extremely relevant within this moral panic this helps identify a number of other factors that may have contributed to this moral panic which has aided the project considerably. Within the Moral panic of Drill music, the youth are presented as an extreme risk that requires management, presented alongside Cohen's original theory there are extreme similarities to the way that the Mods and rockers were presented. Whilst the youth within both moral panics were also considered as a significant threat to society. This was also an occurrence during Drill music's original emergence within Chicago (Fatsis, 2019). Alongside this narrative within the media, it is clear that the moral panic emerged due to high profile acts of violence among young people (Jewkes, 2015). Due to this the creation of a moral panic was undeniably imminent. However, the narrative portrayed within the media was significantly detrimental for many communities, this is due to the self-fulfilling nature of the narrative as the increased level of labelling among these communities, inherently contributed to further crimes that were committed. The labels of a bad influence and dangerous criminals paired with the ban on Drill music which criminalised many young individuals. The ban widened the net for criminality among young black males increasing the deviant labelling reinforcing the criminal narrative. However, this can also be attributed to the newsworthiness of the articles and the media outlets desire to publish stories in relation to violence and conflict as previously mentioned (Jewkes, 2015).

Due to the effects that labelling theory and moral panics presented whilst analysing this contemporary moral panic case study, it is clear to see that both theories have significant effects on youth deviance (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). These effects have ranged from an increase in contact with the juvenile justice system (iatrogenic effect of juvenile justice) and an increased stigmatisation within the media (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). For instance, the news within the UK presented young black males as a societal threat which increased the alienation of their communities and art forms (Chapman, 2021). The main art form that was affected was Drill music the genre and artists were labelled as violent and deviant in nature (Chapman, 2021). Iatrogenic effects of juvenile justice were a significant example of government intervention causing further harm rather than alleviating and negating dangerous effects (Chapman, 2021). Due to the increased labelling young people faced after coming into contact with the justice system and the further implications that it subsequently presented. Many concerns were also identified alongside the moral panic, these concerns were related to a lack of expression amongst marginalised communities due to the government restrictions that were put in place against the genre (Chapman, 2021). This limited artists on when and where they were able to perform whilst also ordering individual artists on what they could wear in public for example, no hoods or hoodies.

During the analysis of the moral panic of Drill music, it was identified that, similarly to Cohen's (Cohen, 1972), original work regarding the Mods and Rockers, it was clear that the media played a significant role in the increased stigmatisation to the targeted groups and communities (Chapman, 2021). Cohens original work on moral panics was also deemed to be relevant within modern day moral panics due to the similarities that were identified (Chapman, 2021), (Fatsis, 2019). The similarities found were partly due to the increased volume of stories portrayed on social and televised media, whilst the news values that were aligned with Drill music included violence and conflict which were of extreme interest to the media as (Jewkes, 2015), identified they can be

pleasurably consumed by the public with great interest. These news values as previously mentioned allowed the news stories regarding Drill music to be kept in a constant media cycle in order to increase coverage on the topic (Jewkes, 2015).

Within the analysis conducted within this chapter, it has been evident that placing a ban on the genre of Drill was an increasingly worrying factor (Fatsis, 2019). Due to the limitation of freedom of expression amongst creators in minority and ethnic communities. This is an incredibly distinct and endangering scenario as vulnerable communities may use freedom of expression to communicate with communities in order to portray and engage diverse issues (Fatsis, 2019).

Chapter 3- The Impacts of Labelling and Moral Panics on Policing Perceptions and Practices

3.1 -Perception of the youth within the police

Labelling and moral panics are extremely prevalent within modern society, this is due to many factors such as the media and the increased amount of awareness that has been placed on them in recent years (Farrington, Osborn and West, 1978), and the many moral panics that have occurred in recent times such as the moral panic surrounding drill music and young people. Due to this, perception and pre-existing views can have significant impacts and effects on the way that policing is conducted (Myhill and Bradford, 2012). Increased labelling amongst the younger generation has presented many issues, including the way youth crime and deviance is assessed and dealt with in the community and in a wider view of policing. This is due to stereotypes being applied to young people for example, the increased labelling of young black men being labelled as criminal, and deviant has led to an increased rate of stop and search cases (Devah Pager, 2009). Many stereotypes have been

identified among police officers and the media, these stereotypes include young people are all criminals and drug users (Lloyd, 2012). These stereotypes are incredibly dangerous and may also underpin the effectiveness of many policing strategies (Lloyd, 2012). Labelling theory reinforces these labels and ideologies as the label may be used by the police during an interaction which may result in a negative reaction, which could in fact reinforce that label (Bernburg, 2019). The media as mentioned within Chapter 2 has a significant effect on the portrayal of young people (Jewkes, 2015). This has been seen in criticising headlines in the UK regarding an increase of violence among young people. This in turn sensationalises the stereotypes attached to young people and youth violence attracting significant attention to the topic in doing so this factor solely can be the reasoning behind the creation of a moral panic within society (Krinsky, 2016). There are various impacts of biased perceptions within police behaviour. Concluding, impacts stem from excessive use of police powers. This includes police perceptions playing a significant role in applying stop and search tactics (Foster, Jones and Pierce, 2022). A biased approach towards young people and people that are from targeted and labelled backgrounds whilst employing these tactics can form a significantly negative response from the targeted groups and communities which may increase stigmatisation and reinforce negative labels (Foster, Jones and Pierce, 2022). Police perceptions are increasingly important due to the fear that a biased perception may leak into day-to-day policing (Brantingham, Valasik and Mohler, 2018). There are various ways that bias may have a significant impact on labelled communities ; the media has also been noted as an instigator of biased perceptions, frequently due to the excessive headlines linked to youth violence (Jewkes, 2015).The media as previously discussed hold excessive weight to the impact that labelling and moral panics have, this in turn has the power to exacerbate the effects and cause more damage as a result (Jewkes, 2015). Whilst excessive use of police powers may also incite an increasingly negative reaction from the labelled or targeted individual/community such as riots or demonstrations.

3.2- Bias within stop and search exacerbating youth deviance

In recent times, there has been increased awareness of stop and search practices this is due to the disproportionate impact on young ethnic communities (Miller *et al.*, 2020). Overtime, this issue has become increasingly problematic; due to recent statistics published identifying the disproportionate levels of stop and search cases among young black males in the UK (Home Office, 2022).

Furthermore, the increased levels have demonstrated an over-use in stop and search tactics, this has identified the need for further tactics to be made available through increased police training.

Statistics showed for every 1,000 white people the number of stop and searches was a percentage of 7.6%, whereas for every thousand black people the stop and search rate was 52.6% (Home Office, 2022). Overall, an increasingly worrying bias within day-to-day policing presents an increasingly difficult challenge (Miller *et al.*, 2020). Linked heavily to labelling theory, policing bias is not a modern-day challenge and has been a significant issue for a number of years. Labelling theory has suggested that individuals and groups who are labelled as deviant are going to be treated in that way by others including the police (Wiley, Slocum and Esbensen, 2013). Through this identification it is clear that if young black men are increasingly labelled as deviant and criminal, then they are also increasingly likely to be targeted in stop and search protocols (Wiley, Slocum and Esbensen, 2013).

Academics have discussed that in order to successfully address the issues regarding disproportionate stop and search rates, it is essential that the broader social and political contexts that may have an impact and contribute to this must also be thoroughly examined. There are various impacts that this may have on individuals and communities that are constantly labelled as criminals and deviants (Critcher, 2008). These impacts are incredibly severe and present further challenges to the future of policing (Critcher, 2008). One of these impacts, is the likelihood that trust between the police and heavily labelled communities will become eroded and these communities are likely to place less faith and trust within the police (Hollway, 2018). Overtime, this can become a severely complex and dividing issue (Hollway, 2018). Recently, the Metropolitan police have been externally reviewed as

institutionally racist, homophobic, and misogynistic. Through this identification, the increased rates at which young black males are stopped and searched could provide an answer for part of this review. Although the stop and search tactic may have proven useful due to its prolific use, it is increasingly vital that further measures are put in place to counter over-using it. This in turn may alleviate some issues among the community regarding the police and the targeted communities.

There is a significant need for further police training on profiling and labelling. Police practice is often influenced by labelling and moral panics, the view that police officers hold and the way that they interact with the public is a significant matter (Bartie, 2010). This is due to the ability to build trust within communities by engaging and interacting with the public in order to benefit the community (Bartie, 2010). One significant impact that labelling and moral panic has on police training is, the continuation of certain stereotypes and bias (Cohen, 2011). These stereotypes can cause significant harm and may be reinforced by police training (Cohen, 2011). Police officers may be trained in a certain way that allows them to judge, identify and view different members of the community differently and associate certain members as increasingly deviant and criminal (Cohen, 2011). As previously identified within stop and search statistics, overtime has led to the over policing of certain communities within the UK. Similarly, with labelling theory, moral panics may also present various challenges to police training. These challenges can range from police officers needing to acknowledge their own biases to the police force adapting community policing strategies to de-escalate situations that are caused by labelling and moral panics (Bennell *et al.*, 2021). The reasoning behind this is due to training programs perpetuating stereotypes concerning certain crimes and the perpetrators due to moral panics that may be occurring during that period in time (Bennell *et al.*, 2021). It can have a significant impact on the communities that are affected as they may be unfairly targeted and face increased stigmatisation. In addition, this may also have further impact on young people within the affected communities as they may become increasingly profiled and subsequently labelled as deviant.

3.3-The effects of Police perception on youth deviancy

Whilst Police training and police perception can have a significant Impact on youth deviance there are also many ways that young people can be impacted by the justice system (Hagan, Shedd and Payne, 2005). However, one of the most impactful factors is police training the reasoning behind this is police training identifies ways to engage with the community to promote a positive outlook and to protect communities. Police training is incredibly important as it can rely on academic research and real-life practice in order to understand how certain practices may impact the community. As identified in Chapter 1 and 2 labelling theory can have a significant impact on young individuals, this is due to the self-fulfilling prophecy (Hagan, Shedd and Payne, 2005). The self-fulfilling prophecy is when a person internalises a label that has been given to them in many cases this label is negative and can have significant damage to their mental health and wellbeing (Zajda, 2019). Through policing if labelling is consistently used among certain communities, then this may lead the community to become significantly distrustful when it comes to the police and other government agencies for instance the justice system (Zajda, 2019).

Through this it is clear to see that if the community is significantly distrustful of the police, then younger members of the community will likely follow (Sharp and Atherton, 2007). This may increase youth deviance due to the heavy labelling potentially causing a moral panic (Sharp and Atherton, 2007). This identifies that police training can have a significant impact through accidental/purposeful biased labelling. However, if police training were to be improved and bias was eliminated from the police force it may encourage communities to continuously engage with the police and increase their trust. Communities may also benefit from community policing; this is due to the trust being broken with the police among a vast majority of communities in the UK (Xu, Fiedler and Flaming, 2005). Community policing would allow for an opportunity to create a meaningful dialogue in which young members can voice their concerns in order to create a positive and safe environment (Xu, Fiedler and Flaming, 2005).

Whilst analysing the effects to police training and the various effects that may occur due to the effects of labelling and moral panics, it has been identified that there are many factors within training that can affect and increase the likelihood of youth deviancy. The factors that may affect this are extremely important and it is vital that they are researched further. Bias among police officers towards certain communities was established as a main effect of labelling and moral panics (Anne, 1997). This is specifically due to police training aiming to focus on the supposed perpetrators of moral panics and subsequently focusing on the certain group for a large amount of time which is increasingly likely to cause uproar and establish distrust for the police in many of those communities (Anne, 1997). Furthermore, this can have significant impact on youth deviance as the communities may become over policed this is a likely factor to significantly increase youth deviance as young people in these communities may feel targeted and labelled (Bernburg, 2019). The labels which are usually negative can become internalised and established in these communities leading to increasingly negative outcomes such as a rise in youth deviance (Bernburg, 2019). Labelling and moral panics has had a severe effect on the systems and strategies in which the police are trained to use. This is evident, with the stop and search practice employed by many constabularies within the police in the UK especially the Metropolitan Police. Moral panics and labelling have been detrimental to the way that stop, and search tactics have been used; this is due to the over policing and over-use of stop and search in regard to black people within the UK (Billingham and Irwin-Rogers, 2022). The statistics identify a significantly higher rate of black people were stopped and searched compared to white people is a significant concern (Billingham and Irwin-Rogers, 2022). This identifies that stop and search is in need of further updating in order to avoid over policing of communities. Furthermore, increased awareness of the overuse of stop and search may allow police officers to use the tactic in an increasingly efficient way in order to avoid bias such as having requirements to warrant a stop and search.

The perception of youth among police officers is also a detrimental effect of moral panics. As mentioned in this chapter a common view among police officers is that they are deviant drug users (Lloyd, 2012). Through analysis this chapter identified that this view could become incredibly detrimental to the way police training and tactics are used. The reasoning behind this is that the negative labels may affect the way that the police operate in different situations (Bernburg, 2019). The use of these labels as previously mentioned, may reinforce certain stereotypes placed on young people such as deviant (Bernburg, 2019). Although the effects of moral panics and labelling are increasingly important many academics have previously accused labelling theory of using circular logic, (Davis 1963). Although, this may be identified in certain situations when used in the context of police training and perceptions it is increasingly likely that labelling has had detrimental effects and has enabled the over policing of communities and increased youth deviancy considerably over time.

Conclusion

To conclude, this dissertation and the research conducted has provided valuable insight into, the key concepts and effects of labelling theory and moral panics and the key links that have been identified to have impact on youth deviancy. The key concepts that were identified were analysed in the context of youth deviance. Concepts that were identified throughout this dissertation were the iatrogenic effects of juvenile justice, and the self-fulfilling prophecy. Concepts such as the iatrogenic effects identified that young people who came into contact with the justice system at a young age can have significant effects on the perception of young people causing increased scrutinization through condemning headlines in the media (Gatti, Tremblay and Vitaro, 2009). Through the analysis of the case study of the contemporary moral panic of Drill music, it was identified that there was an increased scrutinisation of young black men within the media. Media scrutinisation played a significant part in the Metropolitan police identifying Drill music as a key factor of youth violence (Chapman, 2021). This Dissertation also set out in the literature review in chapter one to identify whether or not the literature regarding moral panics would still be relevant if used within today's society. The dissertation analysed the literature thoroughly and within the context of a contemporary moral panic (Drill music) the literature became extremely relevant, Cohens original findings were replicated within the literature for the moral panic surrounding Drill music. This is an incredibly important discovery, as in recent years there have been various developments to culture and society which may have had implications to the original framework of Cohen's moral panic literature. These include the changes to the news media and the exacerbation of events that occurs online or social media platforms.

In light of evidence found, this dissertation identified that police perceptions of young people as drug using deviants are likely to be a manifestation of ongoing moral panics and biases held by the individual (Citcher, 2013). Due to this, the dissertation found that increased bias among the police may be a direct effect of moral panics and subsequent labelling. A direct Impact of this was found to

be stop and search statistics, the findings show that police officers using stop and search were increasingly discriminatory towards black people as the statistics showed a disproportionate difference between the amount of white people stopped compared to the amount of black people stopped (Home Office, 2022). This is an increasingly problematic issue as many prominent individuals across the UK have also identified this discrepancy, highlighting it as a significant issue amongst police forces. Due to this evidence of bias, the dissertation identified recent reports conducted on the Metropolitan Police in which they were identified as institutionally racist and misogynistic (Casey, 2023). Due to this identification from an external review, it presents many issues that may affect the efficacy of this police force as a whole (Casey, 2023). Presented with this information, this dissertation identified it as an ongoing concern in which may have detrimental consequences as to how the Police within the UK operates and navigates society (Casey, 2023).

Another crucial discovery made by this dissertation was the effect that the media has within a moral panic and the effects that were presented to youth deviancy. Within a moral panic, increased scrutinisation among the targeted people/communities is expected as this is the nature of a moral panic. However, in recent years as identified by this dissertation the media has become increasingly powerful (Jewkes, 2015). For example, within the moral panic of Drill music the media had presented young men as a societal threat, whilst these reinforced negative and harmful stereotypes it also increased stigmatisation within many communities which in turn can cause further issues within society. Throughout this dissertation the media was considered to be a strong factor for the influence of a moral panic, this has also been identified within the analysis of Drill music as the articles remained in the media for a significant amount of time. The media was a fundamental factor of causing the moral panic, due to the newsworthiness that Drill music held and the topics that would be covered in articles in reference to Drill music such as violence and harm. These identifiers within the media are extremely popular among the public and as previously mentioned in Chapter 3, violence and harm are consumed by the public with pleasure as the public always has a vested interest in these topics (Jewkes, 2015). Due to the curiosity of members of the public whilst there is

also an interest for the safety of the community (Jewkes, 2015). Although these properties may call to the general public as genuine interest, the constant circulation of these stories heavily impacted and increased the labelling of communities as deviant.

Overall, this dissertation has identified that the effects of labelling and moral panics can have significant effects on youth deviancy. Through this identification the dissertation will present recommendations on how to navigate and police youth deviancy in the context of Labelling and moral panics.

These recommendations have been derived from the analysis conducted on the contemporary moral panic of Drill music and the analysed literature regarding the police perceptions of youth deviancy. The recommendations will aim to identify and alleviate the effects of labelling and moral panics in the context of youth deviancy. The first recommendation is for the government to form a partnership in order to prevent stigmatisation of communities and targeted individuals through news media and social media. This recommendation has been given in order to reduce the amount of labelling that individuals and communities may face. The second and last recommendation the dissertation will provide regarding labelling and moral panics and the links to youth deviancy is: a rejuvenated training program to be provided to new and existing police officers in order to avoid bias within day-to-day policing. This anti-bias training will alleviate issues raised by stop and search statistics and external reviewers who highlighted the extreme biases within the police force that have occurred and increased within recent years. These recommendations may help alleviate the labels and biases that are subjected to young people within the UK.

Reference list

- Anne, B., Melanie (1997) *Youth and youth crime: a moral panic. a content analysis of four Ontario newspapers*. Available at: <https://atrium.lib.uoguelph.ca/xmlui/handle/10214/20082> (Accessed: 12 April 2023).
- Bartie, A. (2010) 'Moral Panics and Glasgow Gangs: Exploring "the New Wave of Glasgow Hooliganism", 1965–1970', *Contemporary British History*, 24(3), pp. 385–408. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13619462.2010.497248>.
- Ben-Yehuda, N. (2009) 'Foreword: Moral Panics--36 Years On', *British Journal of Criminology*, 49(1), pp. 1–3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azn076>.
- Bennell, C. *et al.* (2021) 'Advancing police use of force research and practice: urgent issues and prospects', *Legal and Criminological Psychology* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/lcrp.12191>.
- Bernburg, J.G. (2019) 'Labeling Theory', *Handbooks of Sociology and Social Research*, pp. 179–196. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20779-3_10.
- Billingham, L. and Irwin-Rogers, K. (2022) 'Harmful Responses to "Youth Violence"', *Against Youth Violence*, pp. 150–201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.51952/9781529214086.ch006>.
- Brantingham, P.J., Valasik, M. and Mohler, G.O. (2018) 'Does Predictive Policing Lead to Biased Arrests? Results From a Randomized Controlled Trial', *Statistics and Public Policy*, 5(1), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2330443x.2018.1438940>.
- Brisman, A. and South, N. (2015) 'New "Folk Devils," Denials and Climate Change: Applying the Work of Stanley Cohen to Green Criminology and Environmental Harm', *Critical Criminology*, 23(4), pp. 449–460. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10612-015-9288-1>.
- Casey, B. (2023) 'An independent review into the standards of behaviour and internal culture of the Metropolitan Police Service', *Metropolitan Police* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.met.police.uk/SysSiteAssets/media/downloads/met/about-us/baroness-casey-review/update-march-2023/baroness-casey-review-march-2023.pdf> (Accessed: 17 April 2023).
- Chapman, D. (2021) *The Colour of Racism The Criminalisation of Black Music Culture in Postwar*. Available at: https://crimsoc.hull.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/2021_Chapman_Colour_of_Racism.pdf.

Cohen, S. (1972) *Folk Devils and Moral Panics: The Creation of the Mods and Rockers*. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Cohen, S. (2011) *Folk Devils and Moral Panics*. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203828250>.

Critcher, C. (2008) 'Moral Panic Analysis: Past, Present and Future', *Sociology Compass*, 2(4), pp. 1127–1144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2008.00122.x>.

Critcher, C. (2011) *Critical readings : moral panics and the media*. Maidenhead England: Open University Press ; New York.

Critcher, C. (2013) *Moral panics in the contemporary world*. New York: Bloomsbury Academic.

Dandoy, A. (2014) 'Towards a Bourdieusian frame of moral panic analysis: The history of a moral panic inside the field of humanitarian aid', *Theoretical Criminology*, 19(3), pp. 416–433. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362480614553522>.

DAVIS, R. (1973) 'THE LABELING PERSPECTIVE AND JUVENILE DELINQUENCY', *Doctoral Dissertations* [Preprint]. Available at: https://scholars.unh.edu/dissertation/1025?utm_source=scholars.unh.edu%2Fdissertation%2F1025&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages (Accessed: 14 February 2023).

Devah Pager (2009) *Marked : race, crime, and finding work in an era of mass incarceration*. Chicago, Ill: University Of Chicago Press ; Bristol.

Farrington, D.P. (2014) *Labeling theory : empirical tests*. Taylor & Francis Group.

FARRINGTON, D.P., OSBORN, S.G. and WEST, D.J. (1978) 'THE PERSISTENCE OF LABELLING EFFECTS', *The British Journal of Criminology*, 18(3), pp. 277–284. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.bjc.a046913>.

Fatsis, L. (2019) 'Policing the beats: The criminalisation of UK drill and grime music by the London Metropolitan Police', *The Sociological Review*, 67(6), pp. 1300–1316. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038026119842480>.

Forss Norstedt, H. and Malmqvist, J.E. (2021) *Non-state crime prevention methods : Preventing youth crime, miun.diva-portal.org*. Available at: <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:miun:diva-41212> (Accessed: 6 April 2023).

Foster, K., Jones, M.S. and Pierce, H. (2022) 'Race and Ethnicity Differences in Police Contact and Perceptions of and Attitudes Toward the Police Among Youth', *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, p. 009385482210782. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00938548221078296>.

Gatti, U., Tremblay, R.E. and Vitaro, F. (2009) 'Iatrogenic effect of juvenile justice', *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 50(8), pp. 991–998. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2008.02057.x>.

Gottfredson, M.R. and Hirschi, T. (1990) *A General Theory of Crime*. Stanford University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781503621794>.

Hagan, J., Shedd, C. and Payne, M.R. (2005) 'Race, Ethnicity, and Youth Perceptions of Criminal Injustice', *American Sociological Review*, 70(3), pp. 381–407. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/000312240507000302>.

Herd, G. (2009) *Moral Panics, Sex Panics : Fear and the Fight Over Sexual Rights*. New York, N.Y.: New York University Press.

Hill, J. and Maughan, B. (2001) *Conduct disorders in childhood and adolescence*. Cambridge, U.K. ; New York, Ny: Cambridge University Press.

Hollway, J. (2018) 'Legal Optimism: Restoring Trust in the Criminal Justice System Through Procedural Justice, Positive Psychology and Just Culture Event Reviews', *Master of Applied Positive Psychology (MAPP) Capstone Projects* [Preprint]. Available at: https://repository.upenn.edu/mapp_capstone/151/ (Accessed: 12 April 2023).

Home Office (2022) *Stop and Search*, Gov.uk. Home Office. Available at: <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/crime-justice-and-the-law/policing/stop-and-search/latest>.

Ilan, J. (2019) 'Digital Street Culture Decoded: Why criminalizing drill music is Street Illiterate and Counterproductive', *British Journal Of Criminology*, 60(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azz086>.

Ireland, C.A. et al. (2020) *The Handbook of Collective Violence*. Routledge.

Jewkes, Y. (2015) *Media & crime*. 3rd edn. Los Angeles: Sage, Cop.

Johnson, L.M., Simons, R.L. and Conger, R.D. (2004) 'Criminal Justice System Involvement and Continuity of Youth Crime', *Youth & Society*, 36(1), pp. 3–29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118x03260323>.

KLEIN, M.W. (1986) 'Labeling Theory and Delinquency Policy', *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 13(1), pp. 47–79. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854886013001004>.

Krinsky, C. (2016) *Moral Panics over Contemporary Children and Youth*. Editorial: Routledge.

Krohn, M.D. *et al.* (2019) *Handbook On Crime And Deviance*. S.L.: Springer.

Link, B. (1982) 'Mental Patient Status, Work, and Income: An Examination of the Effects of a Psychiatric Label', *American Sociological Review*, 47(2), p. 202. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2094963>.

Lloyd, C. (2012) 'The stigmatisation of problem drug users: A narrative literature review', *Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy*, 20(2), pp. 85–95. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/09687637.2012.743506>.

Mannion, R. and Small, N. (2019) 'On Folk Devils, Moral Panics and New Wave Public Health', *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 8(12), pp. 678–683. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2019.78>.

Marsh, I. and Melville, G. (2011) *Moral Panics and the British Media: A look at some contemporary 'Folk Devils'*. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/download/30873842/Marsh_Melville_Moral_Panics_and_the_British_Media_March_2011.pdf.

McAra, L. and McVie, S. (2012) 'Negotiated order: The groundwork for a theory of offending pathways', *Criminology & Criminal Justice*, 12(4), pp. 347–375. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748895812455810>.

Miller, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Can police training reduce ethnic/racial disparities in stop and search? Evidence from a multisite UK trial', *Criminology & Public Policy*, 19(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-9133.12524>.

Monteith, K. (2022) 'Ban rap and drill lyrics in the courtroom', *Popular Music*, 41(4), pp. 546–557. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261143022000617>.

Moore, C.L. and Stuart, F. (2021) 'Gang Research in the Twenty-First Century', *Annual Review of Criminology*, 5(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-criminol-030920-094656>.

Myhill, A. and Bradford, B. (2012) 'Can police enhance public confidence by improving quality of service? Results from two surveys in England and Wales', *Policing and Society*, 22(4), pp. 397–425. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10439463.2011.641551>.

Pinkney, C. and Robinson-Edwards, S. (2018) 'Gangs, music and the mediatisation of crime: expressions, violations and validations', *Safer Communities*, 17(2), pp. 103–118. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/sc-01-2017-0004>.

Scott, C.D. (2020) 'Policing Black sound: performing UK Grime and Rap music under routinised surveillance', *Soundings*, 75(75), pp. 55–65. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3898/soun.75.03.2020>.

Shadd Maruna (2013) *Making good : how ex-convicts reform and rebuild their lives*. Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.

Sharp, D. and Atherton, S. (2007) 'To Serve and Protect?: The Experiences of Policing in the Community of Young People from Black and Other Ethnic Minority Groups', *British Journal of Criminology*, 47(5), pp. 746–763. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azm024>.

Spicer, J. (2021) 'The Policing of Cuckooing in "County Lines" Drug dealing: an Ethnographic Study of an Amplification Spiral', *British Journal Of Criminology*, 61(5). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azab027>.

Ugwudike, P. (2015) *The labelling perspective*, bristoluniversitypressdigital.com. Policy Press. Available at: <https://bristoluniversitypressdigital.com/display/book/9781447320227/ch002.xml> (Accessed: 7 March 2023).

Waite-Jones, J.M. and Rodriguez, A.M. (2022) 'Deviance and Labelling', *Psychosocial Approaches to Child and Adolescent Health and Wellbeing*, pp. 145–169. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-99354-2_8.

Wiley, S.A., Slocum, L.A. and Esbensen, F.-A. (2013) 'The unintended consequences of being stopped or arrested: an exploration of the labeling mechanisms through which police contact leads to subsequent delinquency', *Criminology*, 51(4), pp. 927–966. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-9125.12024>.

Williams, F.P., Mcshane, M.D. and Lemert, E. (2016) *Criminology theory : selected classic readings*. London: Routledge.

Xu, Y., Fiedler, M.L. and Flaming, K.H. (2005) 'Discovering the Impact of Community Policing: The Broken Windows Thesis, Collective Efficacy, and Citizens' Judgment', *Journal of Research in Crime and Delinquency*, 42(2), pp. 147–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022427804266544>.

Young, J. (2007) 'The Vertigo of Late Modernity', *The British Journal of Sociology*, 58(4), pp. 736–737. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-4446.2007.00173_15.x.

Zajda, J. (2019) 'Research on Discrimination and Self-fulfilling Prophecy in Schools Globally', *Education and Society*, 37(1), pp. 59–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7459/es/37.1.05>.

Appendix A Research ethics certificate of completion -

The screenshot shows a 'Questionmark' assessment interface. At the top left, it says 'Questionmark' and 'Jan 19 2022 | Logged in as: joshua.castiglione.1907621'. The main title is 'Research Ethics 2017 - for Medicine Science etc'. Below this is a section for 'Assessment Feedback'. The feedback text reads: 'Congratulations, joshua.castiglione.1907621. You have passed the Research Ethics Quiz at 18:30 on Wednesday, 19 January, 2022 scoring 8 out of 10 (80%)'. There are two paragraphs of instructions: 'Please capture a full screenshot to include in your submission to the relevant Research Ethics Panel. (If needed, [instructions on how to take a screenshot](#) are provided in the Research Ethics Canvas course).' and 'Once you have captured the screen you can just close your browser.'. A final line says 'If you want to view the feedback for the individual questions, please browse through them using the "Next Question" button below.'. At the bottom, the total score is displayed as 'Total score: 8 out of 10, 80%'.

Questionmark

Jan 19 2022 | Logged in as: joshua.castiglione.1907621

Research Ethics 2017 - for Medicine Science etc

Assessment Feedback

Congratulations, **joshua.castiglione.1907621**
You have passed the **Research Ethics Quiz** at 18:30 on **Wednesday, 19 January, 2022** scoring **8 out of 10 (80 %)**

Please capture a full screenshot to include in your submission to the relevant Research Ethics Panel. (If needed, [instructions on how to take a screenshot](#) are provided in the Research Ethics Canvas course).

Once you have captured the screen you can just close your browser.

If you want to view the feedback for the individual questions, please browse through them using the "Next Question" button below.

Total score: 8 out of 10, 80%

Appendix B Supervisor Log -

Date of Meeting	Type of Contact (email, phone, in person)	Overview of meeting content (including outcomes)
20/03/23	Microsoft Teams	Discussing literature review
22/03/23	Microsoft Teams	How to progress to chapter 2
29/03/23	Microsoft Teams	Discussing third chapter and introduction/conclusion
1/04/23	Microsoft Teams	Discussion regarding all chapters and comments

Appendix C- originality report -

turnitin ANONYMOUS DISSERTATION JOSHUA CASTIGLIONE FINISHED.docx

1907621

ANGLIA RUSKIN UNIVERSITY
Dissertation Declaration
Title of Award
BA HONS Criminology

Date
14/04/23

Match Overview

3%

Rank	Source	Percentage
1	Submitted to Anglia Ru... Student Paper	1%
2	ses.library.usyd.edu.au Internet Source	<1%
3	link.springer.com Internet Source	<1%
4	Jessica Bouchard, Jen... Publication	<1%
5	www.era.lib.ed.ac.uk Internet Source	<1%
6	Submitted to University...	<1%